

Analysis of Lightning Current Distribution in the Joints of a Carbon Fiber Composite Applied to an Aircraft

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Abstract—The analysis and studies of the effects on aircraft by lightning strikes allow the aerospace industry has valuable information about the phenomenon, reducing damage and guaranteeing a safe flight. However, as it is a random behavior event, in terms of intensity, the number of discharges, and coupling modes, the subject still offers a wide field of research. The discharge usually strikes one extremity of the aircraft and steps out at the other; these points are generally the wingtips, the plane's nose, or the empennage's end. For this reason, any material used in the aircraft structure must safely conduct electrical currents from lightning from the point of impact. Thus, the carbon composites used in the external construction of the aircraft must allow adequate electrical current paths between parts of the structure, minimizing damage to joints and especially preventing the formation of arcing or sparks.

Keywords—Wind Energy; Lightning Protection; Wind Blade.

I. INTRODUCTION

THE carbon fiber composite structures (CFC) have been used in the most varied areas [1], such as automotive applications [2], civil construction [3] and transmission line structures [4], [5]. Additionally, numerous aeronautical structures (commercial or cargo) use composites, including fuselage, wings, and empennage. According to [6], about 50% of the aircraft body is a composite material, Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Composite Solutions Applied [6].

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Metallic aircraft structures, usually composed of aluminum alloys, have been used safely for decades and are electrically conductive to protect an aircraft from lightning [7], [8]. However, protecting the aircraft from lightning and its electrical equipment is still hugely challenging for manufacturers.

It is known that lightning occurs more frequently during take-off and landing than when the aircraft is flying above clouds in commercial aircraft. Usually, two types of effects occur, named direct and indirect effects, both extremely dangerous for the plane. A review of the most common methodologies for fault modeling, CFC dielectric breakdown, can be found in [9], [10].

The current conducted through the aircraft fuselage can generate electric and magnetic fields that can interfere with the aircraft's entire electrical and electronic system or even induce currents in cables adjacent to the aircraft body. These indirect effects are critical for an aircraft in flight and must be prevented to ensure its safety. Therefore, it is crucial to study the indirect effects caused by a high current discharge when conducted through the fuselage of an aircraft, such as the study carried out by [11]. Equally serious, one of the potential problems caused by direct effects is the possibility of sparking between the dielectric gaps when high currents pass through different materials [12]. The currents waveforms are simulated and compared to real applications performed in the high voltage laboratory to evaluate the direct effects of lightning currents on aircraft structures.

Thus, this work simulated and applied real tests in the CFC materials to evaluate the direct effects of lightning currents on aircraft structures. A component (Component "A") of the typical lightning waveform is applied in the studies. The waveform used in this work is described in SAE ARP 5412 [13], and RTCA-DO-160 [14]. The standards describe typical currents used for lightning tests; a representation of this waveform is shown in Figure 2. It is expected that it will be possible to evaluate the damage caused to the material when conducting a high-intensity electric current through the developed methodology. Additionally, computer simulations will be used to validate the results obtained in the laboratory and study, for example, the behavior of the electric current at the junction between plates.

Fig. 2. Typical lightning discharge waveform - four components.

II. THE CFC STRUCTURE

The composition and configuration of CFC materials can be made in various ways. Two parameters that can be adjusted are the percent concentration and the shape of the components. Although compressive strength and tensile strength are still the essential properties of CFCs used in aerostructures, their electrical characteristics are becoming increasingly important.

CFCs, however, consists of two components (resin and carbon fiber) with very different properties. The conductivity difference, for example, results in significant anisotropic characteristics. Carbon fiber typically has a diameter of 8-10 $[\mu\text{m}]$ [15], [16] and a fiber volume fraction of 50-60%. As a first approximation, however, the conductivities of the constituent parts of CFCs can be considered constant and isotropic.

Fig. 3. Protective device models suggested by standard.

As modeling the real geometry of the CFC fibers requires a great computational effort (greater than what is available in the laboratory), a simplified model is used in which the wefts are considered homogeneous. The electrical permittivity, relative magnetic permeability and conductivity values used to model the carbon material were $\epsilon_{carb} = 12$, $\mu_r = 1$ and $\sigma_{carb} = 1 \cdot 10^5 \text{ [S/m]}$ [17], while for the epoxy resin layer a

thickness of 0.202 [mm] , $\epsilon_{res} = 4$ and tangent loss = 0 were used. The CFC material used to simulate the direct effects reported in this work consists of carbon fiber agglomerates immersed in epoxy resin.

The carbon fiber and resin content are 60% and 40%, respectively, and the fibers are continuous, cylindrical with a diameter of $7.1 \text{ }[\mu\text{m}]$. Each bundle contains 12,000 fibers and has a total cross-sectional area of $0.48 \text{ [mm}^2\text{]}$. The material is formed by layers $0.21\% \text{ mm}$ thick, with the first and last two layers oriented at 0° and 90° and the others at 0° , 45° , 90° , -45° , -90° , 45° , 90° , -45° , etc., where eight layers are shown. A metallic mesh was used above the specimen (SPEC) simulating the device used in the real model to protect the aircraft against lightning. The surface metallic mesh was integrated into the modeled SPEC for simulations in the CST software [18].

III. TESTS AND SIMULATIONS

To carry out the direct effects laboratory tests, the respective SPEC were provided by Embraer, which collaborated with this study. The company sent samples to the High Voltage Laboratory to conduct different tests. Some characteristics of this model are described below.

A single layer of CFC is defined as a weft 1×1 , while in a fiber weft, there are an equal number of interlaced threads; the same is repeated in wefts 2×2 and 4×4 , with the wires only displaced [16], [19]. Single weft (0/90) is the most common weft used in CFC and requires only four threads [20]. In the model, the carbon strips are embedded in epoxy resin, forming a solid plate, as shown in Figure 4, which shows the real model used.

Fig. 4. The model for laboratory tests.

For this specific test, cuts are made in the material to leave only the sections connected to the rivets exposed. Thus, it is possible to couple the current meters and analyzes the rivets' current distribution. The SPEC modeled in the software is configured with the closest approximation of the physical characteristics of the model used in the laboratory tests. As a percentage of carbon fiber to the resin used, approximate calculations are natural in software modeling since the manufacturer does not provide this data. However, these data do not compromise the results of the simulations to validate the tests.

Fig. 5. Model created in software to computer simulations.

The current distribution between the metal layers and meshes is analyzed parallel with the electric current passing through the rivets for direct effects studies.

IV. TEST AND SIMULATION METHOD

The high voltage laboratory used a bank of 25 capacitors of 1 uF each to perform this type of test. These capacitors are charged in parallel, and when they reach the required charge, they are discharged through a pneumatic piston, making contact with the conductor positioned on the surface of the SPEC.

In this configuration, a current of 200 kA cannot be applied because the smaller current transformers (meters) are limited to an electric current of up to 150 kA. Another necessary change refers to the application electrode; in this configuration, it is positioned leaning against the plate, Fig. 6, and not spaced at 50 mm as in the standard tests in this type of study. After the test, the four waveforms are collected for each current transformer coupled to the SPEC, presented in the next section.

Fig. 6. Model positioned for laboratory tests with coupled current meters.

In the simulations performed, an electric current of 200 kA, with the waveform of the same characteristic of the tests, was applied to the left side of the model, this wave represents the peak of lightning current, and the current return point was via a connection on the right side. Fig.5 shows the points where the electric current is measured. It is important to note that the measurements performed here are calculations made by the software at specific points that simulate the magnitude of the electric current over time. The software

provides tools, such as current monitors, to perform this simulated measurement.

V. NUMERICAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

A. TESTS RESULTS

Through the tests carried out, it is possible to affirm that the material resisted, without critical damage, the discharge of current equivalent to that of an atmospheric discharge. The damage caused did not compromise its structure, which the good electrical conductivity can explain during the test. When analyzing the material in detail, it is evident that the damage (burned surface, breakage of the metallic mesh) occurred only at the point of application, grounding, and rivet connections. This phenomenon is expected at the application and grounding points, as the passage of current causes a sudden increase in temperature between connections. The rivets are fixed metallic compounds; thus, there are no gaps between the CFC plates. However, the region is particularly affected, especially in the rivets close to the edge of the SPEC. Therefore, it was considered relevant to use a specific layout to analyze the current passage through each rivet. For this, a SPEC with cuts for the connection of four current transformers is used, as shown in Fig. 6.

Fig. 7. Waveforms captured after electric current application. Each waveform represents a section of the plate.

Analyzing the waveforms, Fig. 7, it is essential to note that the current flow through the rivets is not uniform between them. Most of the electrical current is conducted by the side rivets. This phenomenon is observed in all tested SPECs. The damage observed in these regions is analyzed in detail by computer simulations.

Laboratory analyses have physical limitations, which as the impossibility of measuring the currents conducted between the layers. Therefore, computer simulations are a vital tool for research and validation of results, making it possible to understand phenomena of complex investigation in the laboratory.

Fig. 8. Waveforms obtained after the simulations refer to the measurements of the cross sections directed to the rivets.

Fig. 9. Comparison between the waveforms captured from the cross sections directed to the rivets and the SPEC layers.

B. SIMULATIONS RESULTS

The results obtained through the simulations demonstrate that the current conduction pattern between the rivets is repeated. Through Fig. 8 it is possible to verify that the rivets present on the sides of the SPEC conducted waves 1-1 and 1-4, respectively, presenting the highest magnitudes. Measurements taken at the center rivets, represent by waveforms 1-2 and 1-3, show a smaller peak current conduction.

The Fig. 9 shows the comparison between the currents carried by the sections directed to each of the rivets and the currents carried by the layers of the SPEC. The highest peak currents, represented by A1 and A3, are from the upper layers of the SPEC. On the other hand, currents 1-1 and 1-4 are from the sections close to the rivets, where it is possible to verify that the current peak was approximately three times smaller than that conducted in the layers.

These results are exciting because they correspond to the phenomena observed in the laboratory tests, indicating that the simulations are a reliable tool for developing products and methodologies related to the field of electrical withstand of CFC materials when exposed to a high atmospheric discharge.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

Carbon fiber composites are applied to the fuselage of an aircraft. Thus, this work studies the direct effects caused by a high-intensity lightning discharge in a CFC. The approach used considered tests carried out in the laboratory and computer simulations.

The study focused on analyzing the passage of electric current between the rivets of the plates. A high-intensity electric current is applied to one edge of the CFC plate, and the other edge is grounded. Current transformers are coupled in the transverse sections directed to each rivet in laboratory tests to measure the current magnitude between each rivet.

The rivets located on the sides tend to receive a greater electric current intensity. The same is observed when replicated in computer simulations. This effect is also visually observed when the damage to the SPEC after the current has passed is analyzed. The validation of this result is valuable for the manufacturers and developers of these structures.

Finally, an important conclusion is a correlation between the results obtained in the laboratory and simulations. Computer simulations are adequate and promising for this type of analysis and capture relevant information regarding

the study of atmospheric discharges in composite materials.

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